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Application Details	
APPLICATION NUMBER	202441012548
APPLICATION TYPE	ORDINARY APPLICATION
DATE OF FILING	21/02/2024
APPLICANT NAME	1 . Dr. T. Srinivas 2 . Dr. K. Murali 3 . Dr. K. Vijay Kumar 4 . Mr. Chandrakanth Muneshwar 5 . Dr. P. Ganga Reddy 6 . Mr. Ankam Jayaprakash 7 . Dr. D. Sahadevudu 8 . Dr. S.J. Sampath Kumar 9 . Mr. N Ramesh Goud 10 . Mr. Thony Devanna 11 . Dr. D K. Raju 12 . Dr. M. Kumara Swamy
TITLE OF INVENTION	AUTOMATED ARCHIVAL DOCUMENT RESTORATION SYSTEM
FIELD OF INVENTION	COMPUTER SCIENCE
E-MAIL (As Per Record)	patentpointservices@gmail.com
ADDITIONAL-EMAIL (As Per Record)	
E-MAIL (UPDATED Online)	
PRIORITY DATE	
REQUEST FOR EXAMINATION DATE	--
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Application Status

APPLICATION STATUS

Awaiting Request for Examination

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